

Base64,End of File and Steganography to Improve Security in Websites

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Abstract: This research is used to increase the level of security in college projects and make it harder for hidden to know the information which you hide. Here it shows a demo that how to hide the secret data in your projects can be more secured its just simple using base64,end of file and steganography. End of File (EOF) is the steganography method that widely used and it easily implemented in any, combination of Base64 algorithm as encoding and encryption process on data or object before embedded process using EOF method will produce a strong ciphertext algorithm.Now the user get can give their own at this time the data hided can be decoded using that is good because dynamic key as length message, cipher text will be embedded in bytecode using these technique.We can implement this methods in implement this methods in our college projects to ensure the security of our project Base64 algorithm is used to give more security. While user enter the text through the site user enter their details and it is saved in the form of text . So while using the Base64 algorithm the data which user enter can be converted into encrypted format so that the login details can be get more secured.While encoding the text can be hide in image and encoded using steganography and base64 algorithm.Now the user get login at this time the data hided can be decoded using the same way which its encoded and compare the passwords too. Mainly this technique is used to provide security to the website.

I. INTRODUCTION

Base 64 Algorithm it will encode the binary data into 64 stream of printable characters.This was first presented in RFC-1421-Privacy Enhancement for

Electronic Mail in this first done Message Encryption and Authentication Procedures in 1993.The base 64 method is used as the process of encoding messages or file into printable characters, while the EOF method used to hide secret message into the cover media. Steganography which is used to hide secret information into different types of files such as images, video, and audio etc. Problems that occur in steganography is to require different types of algorithms to secure specific data. Here I use these techniques to provide more security in site.Base64 algorithm can be used in various Programming Language like CSS,PHP and JavaScript etc. The security of data in today's digital age is very important, steganography and cryptography can be used to secure data in wherever we need.Base64 and EOF techniques are implemented by using in any programming languages.The main objective of using Base64 is used to convert any file in order to achieve security.Many sites when we search we can see that the URL can be in the format of 64 characters.For eg <https://www.geeksforgeeks> encoded like aHR0cHM6Ly93 like that the encoded url be it uses many tool like character encoding detection, Data URL to image,HTTP Request Online and Validate base 64 like that many tools are used to convert an URL into its encoded format. Like that base64 can be used for any encoding and decoding text formats. But here it shows a combination of Base64,End of File and Steganography for improve security in Project websites.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Heri Nurdianto(Department of Information Technology,Indonesia),Rahmat Hidayat(Computer and Communication Engineering,Malaysia)[1].They are the authors of paper "Combination Base64 and EOF Technique for Steganography".In these it says that steganography consists of a set of methods and techniques which can embed the data into another media.EOF is used to embed the encoding text performed by using Base64. This paper describes a steganography and encoding method using base64 aims to secure many types of files in a particular media or audio etc with a good security and not to damage the stored files and coverage media that used. which is a set of encoding schemes that convert the same binary data to the form of a series of ASCII code. In these paper it shows encoding scheme that convert binary data using base64 algorithm.

R.Rahim(Department of Management Medan ,Indonesia), R Ratnadevi(Electrical Engineering Universitas Bandung,Indonesia D Prayama,E Asri and D Satria(Department Information Technology ,Indonesia)[2].They represent the paper"Base64,End of File and One Time Pad for Improvement Steganography Security". Steganography is a technique to hide secret information into various types of files such as images, video, and audio , the problems that occur in steganography is to require different types of algorithms to secure specific data.. The base64 method is used as the process of encoding messages or files into a printable text, while the EOF method is used to hide secret message into the cover media. The use of EOF and Base64 methods alone is not safe enough because the decoding process using Base64 can be done directly without secret key, to improve the security level of the hidden information One Time Pad algorithm are used as additional security.

Cui Bo;Zheng Weimin;Feng Shengzhong(Computer Science and Information Technology)[3]."New range reduction algorithm using 64-bit integer computation".It is used in the element function library and high performance.Using the 64-bit integer arithmetic unit, all the intermediate computation is optimized for its Parallelism,table size and throughput,and the improved one base on it debases he complexity.In these it defines the 64-bit integer which gives high security to the performance for range reduction

Rini Indrayani (Information Technology, Information Systems and Electrical Engineering)"Human Preception Evaluation toward End of File Steganography Methods Implementation Using Multimedia File"[4]. One popular method used to secure data is the steganography method.In this research, the End of File steganography method is successfully implemented in various types of multimedia,namely image ,audio and the video.Steganography process is done using a variety of secret message sizes,then some evaluationcarried out. End of file which hide the data and access by the user itself.From this we can see that by combination of these three it give more security to the websites.Its according to the user decision to need security to their websites.

III. METHODOLGY

The mechanism which is done by using Base64 Algorithm, End of File and Steganography.

Steps to be Done:

Encoding

- Base64 encoding
- Steganography encoding
- Image name stored in the folder

Decoding

- Get Image name from folder
- Steganography decoding
- Base64 decoding

The message or file is get encoded using base64 algorithm and the encoding result is now in the form of printable text then the encryption using the key after encryption we get a ciphertext.This ciphertext can be embedded using EOF into Stegnography file.

- The key length should be equal to the length of the plaintext
 - The key used should be random and should be used only once
- $$(x) = ((x) + K(x)) \text{ Mod } 26 \text{ (1)}$$
- $$(x) = ((x) + (x)) \text{ Mod } 26 \text{ (2)}$$

<?php

```

function encode($file, $message) {
    // Encode the message into a binary string.
    $binaryMessage = "";
    for ($i = 0; $i < mb_strlen($message); ++$i) {
        $character = ord($message[$i]);
        $binaryMessage .=
str_pad(decbin($character),8,'0', STR_PAD_LEFT);
    }

    // Inject the 'end of text' character into the string.
    $binaryMessage .= '00000011';

    // Load the image into memory.
    $img = imagecreatefromjpeg($file);

    // Get image dimensions.
    $width = imagesx($img);
    $height = imagesy($img);
    $messagePosition = 0;
    for ($y = 0; $y < $height; $y++) {
        for ($x = 0; $x < $width; $x++) {
            if (!isset($binaryMessage[$messagePosition])) {
                // No need to keep processing beyond the end of
the message.
                break 2;
            }

            // Extract the colour.
            $rgb = imagecolorat($img, $x, $y);
            $colors = imagecolorsforindex($img, $rgb);

            $red = $colors['red'];
            $green = $colors['green'];
            $blue = $colors['blue'];
            $alpha = $colors['alpha'];

            // Convert the blue to binary.
            $binaryBlue = str_pad(decbin($blue), 8, '0',
STR_PAD_LEFT);

            // Replace the final bit of the blue colour with our
message.
            $binaryBlue[strlen($binaryBlue) - 1] =
$binaryMessage[$messagePosition];
            $newBlue = bindec($binaryBlue);

            // Inject that new colour back into the image.
            $newColor= imagecolorallocatealpha($img, $red,
$green, $newBlue, $alpha);
            imagesetpixel($img, $x, $y, $newColor);

            // Advance message position.
            $messagePosition++;
        }
    }

    // Save the image to a file.
    $newImage = 'secret.png';
    imagepng($img, $newImage, 9);

    // Destroy the image handler.
    imagedestroy($img);
}

function decode($file) {
    // Read the file into memory.
    $img = imagecreatefrompng($file);

    // Read the message dimensions.
    $width = imagesx($img);
    $height = imagesy($img);

    // Set the message.
    $binaryMessage = "";

    // Initialise message buffer.
    $binaryMessageCharacterParts = [];

    for ($y = 0; $y < $height; $y++) {
        for ($x = 0; $x < $width; $x++) {

            // Extract the colour.
            $rgb = imagecolorat($img, $x, $y);
            $colors=imagecolorsforindex($img, $rgb);

            $blue = $colors['blue'];

            // Convert the blue to binary.
            $binaryBlue = decbin($blue);

            // Extract the least significant bit into out message
buffer..
            $binaryMessageCharacterParts[] =
$binaryBlue[strlen($binaryBlue) - 1];

            if (count($binaryMessageCharacterParts) == 8) {
                // If we have 8 parts to the message buffer we can
update the message string.
                $binaryCharacter = implode(",
$binaryMessageCharacterParts);
                $binaryMessageCharacterParts = [];
                if ($binaryCharacter == '00000011') {
                    // If the 'end of text' character is found then stop
looking for the message.
                    break 2;
                }
            } else {
                // Append the character we found into the message.
                $binaryMessage .= $binaryCharacter;
            }
        }
    }
}

```

```

    }
    }
    }
    // Convert the binary message we have found into
    text.
    $message = "";
    for ($i = 0; $i < strlen($binaryMessage); $i += 8) {
    $character = mb_substr($binaryMessage, $i, 8);
    $message .= chr(bindec($character));
    }
    return $message;
    }
    $file = 'mushroom.jpg';
    $message = 'AADU FILM';
    steganize($file, $message);

    $secretfile = 'secret.png';
    $message = desteganize($secretfile);
    echo $message;
    ?>
    
```

IV. RESULT

First we need an image to hide the data:

This is the secret png inside this we hide a message using base 64 algorithm:

ORIGINAL MESSAGE : THIS IS ONLY STEGANOGRAPHY DEMO

base64Message : VEhJUyBJUyBPTkxZIFNURUdBTK9HUkFQSFkg REVNTw==

Encoded into the file secret.png
 Decoding the file secret.png

Message extracted from Image :

VEhJUyBJUyBPTkxZIFNURUdBTK9HUkFQSFkg REVNTw==

Message Decoded : THIS IS ONLY STEGANOGRAPHY DEMO

V. CONCLUSION

By using these techniques we can secure our data. Many of them uses for some particular cases while doing in these method the data is get more secured in normal we just encode only using base64 but here steganography and end of file it give more security to the site .It concludes that base 64 algorithm is good at information security system for encryption and decryption its just a demo coding using base64,end of file and steganography.

For all types of files can be done as well, this is because before EoF process a file will be convert into printable text formats by using Base64 method, the steganography process with EoF techniques can perform will with Base64 encoding text.Here code is written in PHP and also base64 is available for all languages.

VI. FUTURE WORK

In these it shows a combination of Base64,End of File and Steganography so it give more security .But in now a days the security issues on websites is more for eg payment sites so that like this doesn't give much security it is a medium security will provide so that we can use hashing SHA-256 and SHA-3 using with these combination it may provide more security than this base64 algorithm.By Using these technique with most secure algorithms it will give a good result.

VII. REFERENCES

[1] R Rahim,R Ratnadewi,D Prayama,E Asri and D Satria(2018)"Base64,End of File and One Time Pad for Improvement Steganography Security"
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